

THE INFLUENCE OF TALENT MANAGEMENT, WORK ENVIRONMENT, AND COMPETENCE ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AT THE DEPARTMENT OF COOPERATIVES, MICRO ENTERPRISES, INDUSTRY, AND TRADE OF BINTAN REGENCY

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the influence of talent management, work environment, and competence on employee performance at the Cooperatives, Micro Enterprises, Industry, and Trade Office of Bintan Regency. The population in this study amounted to 80 respondents, using a saturated sampling technique so that the entire population became the sample, namely 80 respondents. The sampling technique was carried out with a saturated sample. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to respondents. The collected data were processed using SPSS software. The results of the study indicate that partially, Talent Management has a significant effect on employee performance with a significance value of <0.001 (<0.05), Work Environment has a significant effect on employee performance with a significance value of 0.002 (<0.05), and Competence has a significant effect on employee performance with a significance value of <0.001 (<0.05). Simultaneously, talent management, work environment, and competence have a significant effect on employee performance with a significance value of <0.001 (<0.05). The Adjusted R Square value is 0.999 or 99.9%, which means that talent management, work environment, and competence are able to explain 99.9% of employee performance variations, while the remaining 0.1% is influenced by other variables not discussed in this study.

Keywords: *Talent Management, Work Environment, Competence*

INTRODUCTION

The Bintan Regency Cooperatives, Micro Enterprises, Industry, and Trade Office (DKUMPP) is a regional government agency responsible for developing the cooperative, micro-enterprise, industry, and trade sectors to support the local economy in this strategic archipelago. As part of the state civil apparatus (ASN), DKUMPP employees play a crucial role in implementing MSME empowerment programs, providing cooperative outreach, and overseeing business licensing, ultimately contributing to regional economic growth and community welfare. However, in the context of local government in Indonesia, employee performance is often a major challenge due to low productivity resulting from a lack of optimal human resource management, which can disrupt the achievement of local economic development targets. Employee performance generally refers to the level of effective and efficient achievement of tasks and responsibilities, which includes work quality, output quantity, and contribution to organizational goals. In the public sector, employee performance is crucial for realizing good governance, as stipulated in Law Number 5 of 2014 concerning the State Civil Apparatus, which emphasizes the role of ASN in quality public services. Talent management is a key factor influencing employee performance, encompassing the identification, development, and retention of high-potential individuals to maximize their contribution to the organization. Effective talent management can enhance employee motivation and loyalty, while suboptimal performance often leads to productivity stagnation. In the context of ASN, talent management is regulated by Minister of PANRB Regulation Number 8 of 2021 concerning Civil Service Talent Management, which emphasizes competency-based principles. However, in the Bintan Regency DKUMPP, talent management issues emerged in the form of a lack of succession programs and specific training for MKM extension staff, leading to low innovation in empowerment programs.

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LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Description Talent management is a new approach to human resource management that is holistic, with a particular emphasis on the process of recruiting, developing, and retaining talented employees to support and advance the organization's superior talent as a long-term strategy (Wicaksana et al., 2021). According to Fatimah et al. (2023), the concept of talent management first emerged in the private sector in the 1990s as an effort to maximize human resource potential to achieve sustainable competitive advantage. This development was triggered by the "war for talent" phenomenon in the United States, where organizations faced significant difficulties in retaining high-quality employees and recruiting potential candidates due to intense competition and a limited talent supply. Talent management then becomes an important component in human resource management strategies with a more structured approach, aimed at attracting more qualified candidates and retaining the best talent.

Previous Research Research conducted by Candraningrum (2023) Title: Influence of Talent Management, Competence and Placement on Employee Performance (Human Resource Management Literature Review) Population and Sample: This study is a literature review and therefore does not use primary empirical samples. The population includes various empirical studies and HR management theories from national and international journals published between 2018–2023, focusing on employees in the public and private sectors in Indonesia. Data sources were obtained from Google Scholar, Mendeley, and university repositories. Method: A qualitative approach using a systematic literature review method. Analysis was conducted through narrative and thematic synthesis of 25 relevant articles. Data validity was checked through source triangulation and the use of inclusion criteria (e.g., Indonesian/English language studies, having independent variables of talent management/competence, and dependent variables of employee performance). Research Results: Talent management has a positive and significant influence on employee performance through career development mechanisms and retention of superior talent. Technical and behavioral competencies are the main predictors of performance, with a stronger effect than job placement. The work environment is not explicitly analyzed, but is mentioned as an indirect supporting factor through job satisfaction. Overall, the integration of these three variables can improve performance by up to 60–75% in the context of government organizations.

Hypothesis

According to Wardani (2020), a hypothesis is a tentative statement or assumption based on theory that can be empirically tested through data collection and analysis. The purpose of hypothesis testing is to determine whether the assumption is supported (accepted) or rejected based on statistical evidence.

Based on the theoretical and empirical framework that has been described, the research hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H1 : Talent management has a significant influence on employee performance at the Cooperatives, Micro, Industry and Trade Service of Bintan Regency.

H2 : The work environment has a significant influence on employee performance at the Cooperatives, Micro, Industry and Trade Service of Bintan Regency.

H3 : Competence has a significant influence on employee performance at the Cooperatives, Micro Enterprises, Industry and Trade Service of Bintan Regency.

H4 : Talent management, work environment, and competency simultaneously have a significant influence on employee performance at the Cooperatives, Micro, Industry and Trade Service of Bintan Regency.

METHOD

Research Design Research design is a systematic framework to guide the entire research process, ensuring it remains focused and measurable. This framework encompasses the selection of data collection instruments, population and sample determination, data collection stages, and the analytical methods to be used. Syafina and Harahap (2020) state that research design in a quantitative approach serves as a primary roadmap, ensuring a structured process, resulting in valid and reliable data. This study relies on secondary data sourced from official agency documents, annual reports, employee performance archives, and the internal database of the Bintan Regency Cooperatives, Micro, Industry, and Trade Office. The use of secondary data was chosen due to its time and cost efficiency, as well as its ability to provide a comprehensive picture of the relationships between variables without requiring a primary survey.

Operational Variables According to Sedarmayani (2020), the work environment is everything that is around employees, both physical (such as room layout, lighting, temperature, noise, cleanliness, and supporting facilities) and non-physical (such as relationships between employees, organizational culture, leadership style, communication, and internal policies), which together affect the health, comfort, satisfaction, and work productivity of employees.

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Population and Sample A research population is defined as the entire group of entities, whether individuals, groups, institutions, events, or objects, that are the primary focus of generalizing study results. A population encompasses all units of analysis that possess characteristics relevant to the research objectives, allowing representative conclusions to be drawn from the data obtained. As stated by Swarjana (2022), a population is the complete set of subjects or entities targeted for description or generalization in research, and serves as a reference for determining the sample for further analysis.

Table Population

No	Description	Population (people)
1	civil servant	28
2	First Aid Kit	12
3	MSME Companion	20
4	Cooperative Companion	20
Total		80

Source: Department Cooperatives, Micro-Enterprises, Industry and Trade of Bintan Regency(2026)

This test is conducted to determine the partial influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The following is the calculated t formula:

$$t_{hitung} = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}}$$

Information:

- t = significance level (tcount) which is then compared with the t table
- r = Correlation coefficient
- n = number of samples

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the results of the multiple regression test above, multiple regression can be formulated as follows:

$$Y = 1.220 + 0.469x + 0.091z + 0.885w$$

Regression formula:

1. The constant value of 1.220 indicates that if all independent variables have a value of zero or do not change, the performance level remains at 1.220.
2. The regression coefficient for Talent Management is 0.469, indicating that Talent Management has a positive effect on performance. Assuming other independent variables remain constant, each unit increase in Talent Management will increase creativity by 0.469.
3. The regression coefficient for Work Environment is 0.091, indicating that Work Environment has a positive impact on Performance. Holding the other independent variables constant, each one-unit increase in Work Environment will increase Performance by 0.091.
4. The regression coefficient for Competence is 0.885. This indicates that Competence has a positive influence on performance. Holding other independent variables constant, each one-unit increase in Competence will increase performance by 0.885.

Hypothesis Testing

The results of the coefficient of determination analysis test can be seen in the following table.

Table Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.718a	.515	.999	.60308

Based on the table above, the Adjusted R Square value of 0.999, or 99.9%, indicates that Talent Management, Work Environment, and Competence collectively have a 99.9% influence on performance. Meanwhile, the remaining 0.1% is influenced by other variables not included in this research model.

Discussion

From the results of hypothesis testing, it is known that talent management has a significant influence on employee performance. Talent management is a systematic process in identifying, developing, and retaining high-potential individuals to maximize their contribution to the organization, which is an important factor in improving performance because it allows employees to increase motivation, loyalty, and innovation through succession programs, special training, and talent retention, resulting in operational efficiency and more optimal achievement of organizational targets in the public sector such as the development of MSMEs and cooperatives at the Office of Cooperatives, Micro Enterprises, Industry, and Trade of Bintan Regency. Employee talent management is a holistic, competency-based strategy that has a direct cause-and-effect relationship as a benchmark for achieving high performance, both in routine situations and challenges such as post-pandemic adaptation in MSME counseling or business licensing supervision at the DKUMPP of Bintan Regency, where suboptimal talent management can lead to slow growth of the cooperative sector and low innovation in local economic empowerment programs.

From the results of the questionnaire distribution obtained from the respondents, it is known that respondents believe that managerial support can improve employee performance because it fulfills emotional and social needs through organizational attention to employee contributions, employees agree that employee career development will be able to build optimal capabilities so as to encourage quality MSME program output, respondents agree that rewards & recognition will make employees more motivated in counseling and supervisory tasks, respondents agree that intrinsic and extrinsic recognition will certainly be the basis for employees to feel appreciated so as to produce stable performance, and employees with good talent management will certainly be able to produce good and satisfying work results due to the continuous development of individual potential. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Arfati (2024), Sari (2025), Candraningrum (2023), and Anindita & Santoso (2021) which states that talent management has a significant influence on employee performance.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Talent Management has a significant influence on employee performance at the Cooperatives, Micro Enterprises, Industry, and Trade Service of Bintan Regency, with a significance value of <0.001 (<0.05). The first hypothesis is accepted.
2. The work environment has a significant effect on employee performance at the Cooperatives, Micro Enterprises, Industry, and Trade Service of Bintan Regency, with a significance value of 0.002 (<0.05). The second hypothesis is accepted.
3. Competence has a significant effect on employee performance at the Cooperatives, Micro Enterprises, Industry, and Trade Service of Bintan Regency, with a significance value of <0.001 (<0.05). The third hypothesis is accepted.
4. Talent Management, Work Environment, and Competence simultaneously have a significant effect on employee performance at the Cooperatives, Micro Enterprises, Industry, and Trade Office of Bintan Regency with a significance value of F test of <0.001 (<0.05) and an Adjusted R Square of 0.999 or 99.9%. The fourth hypothesis is accepted.

SUGGESTION

From the research results that have been obtained, the suggestions that can be given to the Cooperatives, Micro Enterprises, Industry and Trade Service of Bintan Regency are as follows:

1. The research results show that talent management significantly impacts employee performance. Suggestions include: The Bintan Regency Cooperatives, Micro Enterprises, Industry, and Trade Office needs to improve the implementation of talent management in a more structured and sustainable manner through a holistic talent development program. For example, conducting special training for MSME and cooperative extension workers, developing a competency-based leadership succession program, and implementing a rewards and recognition system (intrinsic and extrinsic awards) for high-performing employees in innovative empowerment programs. This will increase employee motivation, loyalty, and innovation capabilities, thereby significantly improving performance in extension, business licensing supervision, and the growth of the MSME and cooperative sectors.
2. The research findings show that the work environment significantly impacts employee performance. Suggestions include fostering a more conducive work environment, both physically and non-physically. For example, improving physical facilities such as collaborative workspaces, adequate lighting and ventilation, access to technology to support MSME monitoring (such as laptops, data analysis software, and a stable internet connection), and strengthening organizational culture through open communication, supportive superiors, and a sense of psychological security for employees to innovate without excessive pressure. This will ensure employees are more comfortable, motivated, and productive in carrying out fieldwork and developing local economic programs.
3. The research findings indicate that competency significantly impacts employee performance. The Bintan Regency Cooperatives, Micro Enterprises, Industry, and Trade Office recommends focused employee competency development, particularly in technical and digital competencies relevant to the demands of the post-pandemic era. For example, ongoing training on digital MSME data management, the use of online platforms for cooperative registration, micro-enterprise data analysis, and technology-based outreach skills is needed. Furthermore, regular competency assessments and individual development plans aligned with job requirements should be conducted. These steps will reduce errors, accelerate adaptation to new regulations, and improve operational efficiency and service quality for businesses.
4. The research findings show that talent management, work environment, and competency collectively have a significant impact on employee performance (contributing up to 99.9%). The recommendation is that the Bintan Regency Cooperatives, Micro Enterprises, Industry, and Trade Office needs to integrate these three variables into a single, integrated and sustainable human resource development strategy. For example, designing a talent-based HR transformation program that includes strengthening talent management, improving the quality of the work environment (physical and non-physical), and simultaneously developing competencies. This policy can be realized through an annual action plan involving periodic evaluations, special budget allocations, and collaboration with external parties such as the Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs, the Riau Islands Province Regional Personnel Agency, or private technology partners. With this integrated approach, the office can create an adaptive work ecosystem, encourage superior employee performance, and accelerate the achievement of regional economic development targets, increasing the number of active MSMEs, cooperative growth, and optimal contribution to the Bintan Regency economy.

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